

TELMISARTAN; IMPACT ON TRIGLYCERIDES AND C - REACTIVE PROTEIN (CRP) ON NON-OBESE HYPERTENSIVE. A RANDOMIZED CONTROL TRIAL**Dr. Fouzia Aijaz Shaikh¹, Dr Aqsa Huzaif Shaikh², Dr. Talha Shaikh³, Prof Dr. Naila Masood⁴, Prof. Dr Imran Ali Shaikh⁵, Dr Zareen Chang⁶**¹Senior lecturer, Liaquat University of medical and health sciences Jamshoro Sind, Pakistan²Post graduate, LUMHS Jamshoro.³ BDS, Lecturer Liaquat University of medical and health sciences Jamshoro Sind, Pakistan Department of Biochemistry⁴MD Professor of Medicine, Indus medical college @ UMS TMK, Sind, Pakistan⁵Professor of Medicine Liaquat University of medical and health sciences Jamshoro Sindh, Pakistan⁶Sinologist , Ghazali center saddar Hyderabad⁴nailanasood3@yahoo.com, ⁵imran2naila@yahoo.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16886190>**Keywords**CRP, Telmisartan ,
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Prof. Dr Imran Ali Shaikh**Abstract**

Objective: To assess the positive impact of Telmisartan on triglycerides and C-reactive protein in non-obese hypertensive adults of Hyderabad. **Study Design:** Randomized control trial. **Place and Duration of Study:** saddar clinics Hyderabad, Sindh. **Methodology:** Two groups each of 74 adults' non obese hypertensive with raised levels of CRP and triglycerides were selected from clinics of saddar Hyderabad after randomization. Group A, 74 was on Telmisartan and group B was on amlodipine or beta blockers. All patients were included by cluster randomization. The dose of Telmisartan was 80 mg od for 6 months. Three sets of serology tests were obtained including CRP, Serum triglycerides at interval of 0, 12 th and 24 th week. To assess the homogeneity of the Telmisartan and control groups at baseline: continuous variables, independent t test was used. Paired t-tests were conducted for normally distributed data. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant across all analyses. **Results;** the mean age of the patients was 48.5 ± 8.9 vs. 49.1 ± 9.2 years. A significant mean difference of CRP level was observed in between groups. CRP reduction was significant, p value was 0.04 in telmisartan group while 0.06 in other group. Triglyceride was reduced more significantly < 0.001 after 6 months in .telmisartan group. Interestingly female patients benefited more than males. The Blood pressure was moderately reduced in telmisartan group p value <0.001 while other group shown non-significant reduction, p value was 0.15. **Conclusion.** Telmisartan is providing additional benefits in addition of reduction of blood pressure .it has unique properties of reduction of CRP and triglycerides.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is a leading cause of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. The impact of increased blood pressure is aggressively complicated when

associated with dysregulated levels of inflammatory markers and dyslipidemia.

Despite of that fact, hypertension is a root cause of many vascular complications, only 54% of adults with

hypertension are diagnosed properly, half of diagnosed patients are compliant to treatment, and less than one third achieved adequate control of blood pressure¹.

Among hundreds of races, Asians are enormously get benefits of controlled blood pressure, such as lower incidence of cardiovascular disease, stroke, coronary artery disease and heart failure as compared to Western populations².

, More than one billion population is residing in low to middle income countries, and contains two third of hypertensive population. In Pakistan every fourth person is suffering from hypertension³

Hypertension can be controlled by changing in life styles, diet , exercise and avoidance of stress. Just control of blood pressure prevents damage to eight vital organs of body.⁴

The blood pressure fluctuations are very much important to select anti-hypertensive agent. The ambulatory blood pressure monitoring can assess fluctuations. It detects masked hypertension; and predict cardiovascular events and deaths more accurately than office blood pressure.⁵ Blood pressure fluctuation refers to the degree of change in blood pressure within a certain time; this fluctuation is also called Blood pressure variability.⁶

Risk should also be estimated using specific markers, such as albuminuria or increased plasma creatinine, left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH), and subclinical vascular damage, and preexisting CV, cerebrovascular, and renal pathologies are also taken into account.⁷

There are many groups of anti-hypertensive available as well as different societies have been published guide lines to control hypertension. Among ARBs, Telmisartan has thousands time more affinity for the AT1 receptor than for the AT2 receptor⁸. It metabolically increased the mRNA expression of adiponectin and plays role in insulin sensitivity .

One study suggested that combination with telmisartan is better choice with mild renal impairment in Korean hypertensive patients.⁹

Telmisartan has been exerted action by PPAR γ agonistic properties, including improved insulin resistance.¹⁰ it is well tolerated and potentially considered an alternative therapy in patients with cardiovascular disease or high-risk diabetes.¹¹

The hypertensive patients have an elevated CRP concentrations than in non-hypertensive populations even after risk factors modifications.¹²

Telmisartan has shown a role in improvement of glucose and lipid metabolism, insulin resistance, and decreasing parameters of metabolic syndrome.¹³

The rationale for this research is to know positive impact of telmisartan over triglycerides and CRP in mild to moderate hypertensive patients in comparison to other anti hypertensive in non diabetics and non obese patients of Hyderabad Sindh.

Material and methods

This Study was conducted at sadder clinics Hyderabad after obtained proper approval. . This clinic based randomized control trial was include 74 patients of hypertension with triglyceredemia and raised CRP on telmisartan(group A) and 74 patients with raised levels of triglycerides and raised CRP on other antihypertensive, beta blocker or calcium channel blockers(group B or control group) .

The sample size was calculated by taking prevalence of hypertension in Pakistan is 16%, confidence level 95%. Sampling technique was cluster randomization.

The numbers were assigned by research randomizer software.

The mean duration of study was 6 months. A proper questionnaire was used to collect data from all the cases and controls, which recorded and filed. After history, clinical examination, BMI, blood pressure, antihypertensive medications of each groups were noted. The blood samples were collected included serum triglycerides after 10 hours fasting state by 5 cc disposable syringe, C reactive protein level , and sent to Diagnostic and research laboratory sadder or main branch LUMHS.

The hypertriglyceridemia was considered > 200mg /dl and CRP was more than 6mg/dl.

After 3 months, reduction of at least 30% of Triglycerides, CRP and blood pressure by taking Telmisartan was considered significant. After 6 months 50 % reduction in triglycerides, CRP and blood pressures was considered significant.

Telmisartan was given at standard dose of 80 mg daily for 6 months.

The serum levels of CRP and triglycerides was repeated 0, 3months and 6 months.

The statistical analysis for the current study was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 22.

Descriptive Statistics

Initial data analysis involved descriptive statistics to summarize the study population's baseline characteristics.

The continuous variables, triglycerides, C-reactive protein, blood pressure, and body mass index, were calculated as mean ± standard deviation (SD). Categorical variables, including gender, comorbid conditions, and medication type, were calculated in frequencies and percentages (%). To assess the homogeneity of the Telmisartan and control groups at baseline: continuous variables, independent t test was used. For categorical variables, such as sex distribution and presence of comorbidities, the Chi-square test was used. When expected cell counts were less than 5, the Fisher's exact test was employed to ensure statistical robustness.

Paired t-tests were conducted for normally distributed data, These tests compared TG, CRP, and BP levels at baseline vs. 3 months (with a predefined clinical target of ≥30% reduction) and at baseline vs. 6 months.

To compare the longitudinal changes in outcome measures between the Telmisartan and control groups: Repeated Measures Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant across all analyses.

Results

The mean age of the patients was 48.5 ± 8.9 vs. 49.1 ± 9.2 years (p=0.68). (Table 1)

Gender distribution showed that Male/Female: 50/24 vs. 52/22 (p=0.72) The BMI of the patients was

24.6 ± 1.2 vs. 24.8 ± 1.3 kg/m² (p=0.32). The Residence was Urban/Rural: 38/36 vs. 40/34 (p=0.74)

The triglycerides was observed significantly lower with telmisartan then control

Control Group: Minimal change over 6 months (278.4 → 273.8 mg/dL; p=0.85)

Telmisartan Group: Significant reduction (310.5 → 155.3 mg/dL; p<0.001) (Table 2)

A significant mean difference of CRP level was observed in between groups. Control: 1.2% at 3 months; 2.4% at 6 months and in Telmisartan: 30.1% at 3 months; 49.4% at 6 months as shown in (Table 3).

Gender-Based reduction in triglycerides was shown in (Table 4), Control Group: Male: 1.5%, Female: 2.1% (p=0.62) and in Telmisartan Group: Male: 48.3% and in Female: 53.2% (p=0.04).

The CRP was also shown a marked difference in telmisartan group vs control group CRP Reduction at 6 Months: Control Group: Male: 2.0%, Female: 3.0% (p=0.41) and Telmisartan Group: Male: 47.8% and Female: 52.6% (p=0.03)

The blood pressure was also significantly reduced in treatment group than control (Table 5) Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP): Control Group: 148.2 → 145.5 mmHg (p=0.15), Telmisartan Group: 150.1 → 128.3 mmHg (p<0.001), Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP): Control Group: 92.4 → 90.9 mmHg (p=0.27) and Telmisartan Group: 93.6 → 79.5 mmHg (p<0.001)

So telmisartan showed excellent reduction of TG and CRP in group treated by telmisartan (Table 6) TG ↓ vs. SBP ↓: r=0.52 (p<0.001), TG ↓ vs. DBP ↓: r=0.48 (p<0.001) and CRP ↓ vs. SBP ↓: r=0.44 (p=0.002)

Table 1: Group demographic variables of patients

Variable	Control Group (n=74)	Telmisartan Group (n=74)	p-value
Age (years)	48.5 ± 8.9	49.1 ± 9.2	0.68
Gender (Male/Female)	50 / 24	52 / 22	0.72
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.6 ± 1.2	24.8 ± 1.3	0.32
Residence (Urban/Rural)	38 / 36	40 / 34	0.74

Table 2: Comparison of Triglycerides (TG) and CRP Levels at Baseline, 3 Months, and 6 Months

Parameter	Group	Baseline	3 Months	6 Months	p-value (Time Effect)
TG (mg/dL)	Control	278.4 ± 72.1	275.2 ± 70.3	273.8 ± 71.5	0.85 (NS)
	Telmisartan	310.5 ± 85.6	217.4 ± 64.2*	155.3 ± 48.7*	<0.001
CRP (mg/dL)	Control	8.2 ± 0.8	8.1 ± 0.7	8.0 ± 0.8	0.42 (NS)
	Telmisartan	8.3 ± 0.9	5.8 ± 0.6*	4.2 ± 0.5*	<0.001

Table 3: Percentage Reduction in TG and CRP After 3 and 6 Months

Parameter	Group	Reduction at 3 Months (%)	Reduction at 6 Months (%)	p-value (Group × Time Interaction)
TG	Control	1.1%	1.7%	<0.001
	Telmisartan	30.0%*	50.0%*	
CRP	Control	1.2%	2.4%	<0.001
	Telmisartan	30.1%*	49.4%*	

Table 4: Subgroup Analysis by Gender (Triglycerides and CRP Reduction at 6 Months)

Parameter	Group	Male (n=102)	Female (n=46)	p-value (Gender × Group)
TG Reduction (%)	Control	1.5%	2.1%	0.62
	Telmisartan	48.3%*	53.2%*	0.04
CRP Reduction (%)	Control	2.0%	3.0%	0.41
	Telmisartan	47.8%*	52.6%*	0.03

Table 5: Blood Pressure Changes (SBP/DBP) Over 6 Months

Parameter	Group	Baseline	3 Months	6 Months	p-value (Time Effect)
SBP (mmHg)	Control	148.2 ± 8.5	146.8 ± 7.9	145.5 ± 8.1	0.15 (NS)

Parameter	Group	Baseline	3 Months	6 Months	p-value (Time Effect)
DBP (mmHg)	Telmisartan	150.1 ± 9.2	135.4 ± 6.8*	128.3 ± 5.7*	<0.001
	Control	92.4 ± 5.3	91.7 ± 5.1	90.9 ± 4.8	0.27 (NS)
	Telmisartan	93.6 ± 5.8	84.2 ± 4.3*	79.5 ± 3.9*	<0.001

Table 6: Correlation between TG Reduction and BP Reduction in Telmisartan Group

Variable	Pearson's r	p-value
TG ↓ vs. SBP ↓	0.52	<0.001
TG ↓ vs. DBP ↓	0.48	<0.001
CRP ↓ vs. SBP ↓	0.44	0.002

Discussion

This clinic-based randomized controlled trial, unique one over two different groups of patients related to Sindh province, evaluated the effects of Telmisartan versus other antihypertensive (beta-blockers/calcium channel blockers) on triglycerides, C-reactive protein, and blood pressure in hypertensive patients with hypertriglyceridemia and elevated CRP with normal BMI.

Telmisartan has shown superior efficacy in stage 1 and 2 hypertensive patients with single daily dosing¹⁴, and this matched with our study. The blood pressure was also significantly reduced in telmisartan group than control (Table 5) Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP): Control Group: 148.2 → 145.5 mmHg (p=0.15), Telmisartan Group: 150.1 → 128.3 mmHg (p<0.001), Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP): Control Group: 92.4 → 90.9 mmHg (p=0.27) and Telmisartan Group: 93.6 → 79.5 mmHg (p<0.001). so blood pressure is controlled well was in the Telmisartan group, with ~ 15% reduction in systolic BP (SBP) and ~ 16% in diastolic BP (DBP).

In our study, Telmisartan significantly reduced TG and CRP levels by ~ 50% over 6 months, while the control group showed no significant changes and these findings are match able to the Study over 12 weeks of administration of telmisartan in addition to other conventional medicines, significantly improved insulin resistance, sugar levels, and reduction in CRP with other potential inflammatory markers.¹⁵

Our study has shown an interesting fact that females exhibited slightly greater TG/CRP reductions than males on Telmisartan, suggesting possible gender-specific metabolic benefits and many cardio metabolic events are related to Triglycerides and CRP. These findings are matched with one older research of 30 patients were kept on moderate dose of telmisartan, for 3 months demonstrated increased HDL and decreased atherogenic lipids.¹⁶

In a recent trial of metabolically associated fatty liver disease patients, administration of low dose telmisartan for 2 months was as effective as weight reducing agent for 12 weeks.¹⁷

Telmisartan, is not only control blood pressure but improves dyslipidemia in hypertensive patients.¹⁸

Clinical Implications

Telmisartan is superior to conventional antihypertensive in patients with hypertension + hypertriglyceridemia + elevated CRP, offering triple benefits (BP, lipids, inflammation).

Females may derive additional metabolic benefits, warranting gender-specific considerations in treatment.

Long-term studies are needed to assess cardiovascular outcome reductions (e.g., myocardial infarction, stroke) in such patients.

Conclusion

Telmisartan demonstrates significant triglyceride-lowering, anti-inflammatory, and antihypertensive effects in high-risk hypertensives, supporting its use as a first-line agent in metabolic syndrome-associated hypertension. Future research should explore hard cardiovascular endpoints and optimal dosing strategies.

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